

EXAMINING GENDER DIFFERENCES IN PERFORMANCE AND RETENTION OF SIMPLE HARMONIC MOTION THROUGH TECHNOLOGY-ENHANCED GUIDED-INQUIRY AMONG PHYSICS STUDENTS

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated gender differences in performance and retention in the Physics concept of Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM) using Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) among senior secondary school students. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental design, specifically the non-randomized pre-test, post-test control group design, was adopted. The study population comprised 998 Senior Secondary Two Physics students from ten public secondary schools in Itu Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 108 students from two intact classes one urban and one rural assigned to the experimental and control groups. The experimental group received instruction through TEGI, while the control group was taught using the traditional expository method. A researcher-developed instrument titled Physics Performance Test (PPT) was used for pre-test, post-test, and retention tests. The instrument was validated by three experts from the University of Uyo, and its reliability, determined using the test-retest method, yielded a coefficient of 0.85. Data were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) tested the hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed a significant difference in the performance and retention of students taught SHM using TEGI compared to the expository method. However, no significant difference in retention was observed between male and female students in the experimental group. It was concluded that TEGI enhances students' performance and retention in Physics. Therefore, teachers should adopt technology-based instructional strategies, and stakeholders should support teacher ICT training.

Keywords: Gender, Performance, Retention, Simple Harmonic Motion, Technology-Enhanced Guided Inquiry

Introduction

Physics remains one of the most important science subjects in secondary school curricula in Nigeria due to its central role in technological and scientific development. However, students' performance in Physics has consistently been below expectations, especially in core topics like Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM), which require both conceptual understanding and mathematical competence (WAEC, 2022). The difficulty in mastering such abstract topics is compounded by the prevalent use of traditional expository teaching methods, which limit students' active engagement and often fail to foster long-term retention of knowledge (Adesoji and Olatunbosun, 2008). In response, there has been a growing call for the incorporation of innovative, student-centered pedagogical

strategies that leverage technology and enhance interactive learning experiences.

Guided-Inquiry methods, especially when combined with technology-enhanced tools such as PhET simulations, have shown promise in improving students' comprehension and retention of Physics concepts. These strategies shift the instructional focus from passive reception to active exploration and discovery, allowing students to construct knowledge through hands-on experiences and collaborative learning (Eze et al, 2020). Research has demonstrated that technology-enhanced guided-inquiry not only stimulates students' interest in science subjects but also helps them visualize and understand abstract principles like oscillations in SHM (Nwankwo and Okeke, 2021). Consequently, integrating digital

simulations with inquiry-based instruction may bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical understanding among secondary school students.

The expository method, also known as the direct or lecture method, is a traditional teacher-centered instructional approach where the teacher delivers information systematically while students passively receive and absorb content. It remains one of the most commonly employed strategies in Nigerian secondary schools due to its efficiency in covering large content areas within limited time (Obeka, 2018). Despite its popularity, the expository method has been criticized for promoting rote memorization over conceptual understanding and limiting student engagement, particularly in subjects like Physics that require hands-on and critical thinking

Experiences (Ibitoye and Ajayi, 2021). Students often face challenges in retention and application of knowledge taught through this method, as it rarely fosters inquiry, creativity, or learner autonomy (Eze & Okonkwo, 2020). However, when properly implemented with visual aids, analogies, and well-structured presentations, the method can support foundational knowledge, especially when introducing new or abstract topics (Akinbobola, 2022).

Despite the recognized benefits of such approaches, gender disparities in science achievement and retention persist in the Nigerian educational context. Studies have suggested that male students tend to outperform their female counterparts in Physics due to a variety of socio-cultural and psychological factors, including stereotypes, classroom dynamics, and differences in self-efficacy (Ogunleye and Adepoju, 2020). These gender-based discrepancies may also influence how learners engage with inquiry-based technologies, potentially affecting their performance and long-

term retention. Investigating how these instructional methods impact male and female students differently could offer valuable insights into designing more inclusive science education practices. Moreover, existing literature has highlighted the effectiveness of guided-inquiry strategies in enhancing retention of science concepts. Okoli and Eze (2021), for instance, reported that students taught using inquiry-based learning retained Physics concepts more effectively than those exposed to traditional teaching methods. Similarly, Achor, Imoko, and Uloko (2009) found that students who engaged in ethno science and inquiry-based activities exhibited improved long-term retention. However, limited empirical studies have examined these outcomes in the specific context of Simple Harmonic Motion or have explored gender-based variations in retention using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry approaches in Nigerian schools.

Empirical findings from various Nigerian studies continue to reinforce the relevance of guided-inquiry and technology-enhanced approaches in addressing performance and retention gaps among male and female Physics students. For instance, Nwafor and Obiekwe (2020) carried out a study involving 140 senior secondary students in Imo State to assess the impact of inquiry-based learning on gender differences in academic performance in Physics. Their results indicated that while both genders benefited from the strategy, male students showed higher mean scores in both immediate performance and long-term retention. In a similar vein, Umar and Lawal (2021) employed a quasi-experimental design with 180 students in Kano State to determine the effect of technology-aided inquiry-based instruction on students' retention in mechanics concepts. The study reported a significant improvement in retention, especially for male students, who were found to engage more

confidently with the PhET simulations than females. Furthermore, Emembolu and Ezeani (2019) explored the gendered effect of simulation-enhanced instruction in secondary school Physics classrooms in Enugu State. Their research, using a sample of 150 students, revealed that simulation-supported guided-inquiry instruction improved retention across both genders, but with a statistically higher advantage for males in topics such as oscillation and wave motion. Lastly, Adeyemi and Fagbola (2022) conducted a comparative study of traditional and simulation-based instruction in Ekiti State, using a sample of 200 SS2 students. Their findings confirmed that technology-enhanced guided-inquiry not only boosted students' performance but also highlighted a persistent gender gap in favor of male learners, particularly in conceptually dense areas like Simple Harmonic Motion. Therefore, this study is necessitated by the need to examine the gender differences in performance and retention of Simple Harmonic Motion concepts among Physics students using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry methods. By addressing this gap, the research aims to contribute to the development of effective pedagogical models that cater to diverse learner needs, thereby promoting equity, engagement, and improved learning outcomes in Nigerian science classrooms.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the crucial role Physics plays in technological advancement and scientific development, students' academic achievement and retention in the subject remain persistently low in Nigerian secondary schools, as reflected in repeated reports by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC, 2020). One key factor contributing to this underperformance is the widespread reliance on the expository

method of teaching, which emphasizes content delivery through lectures and rote memorization rather than active learner engagement. Although this method may be efficient for introducing abstract topics, it often fails to promote deep conceptual understanding and long-term retention of scientific principles like Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM), a core Physics topic known for its abstractness and mathematical complexity (Ibitoye and Ajayi, 2021; Obeka, 2018). Moreover, while alternative approaches such as guided-inquiry and technology-enhanced simulations have been shown to foster deeper learning and cognitive engagement (Achor et al. 2021), their adoption in Nigerian classrooms is still limited. This is particularly concerning given

That gender disparities in science education persist, with studies indicating variations in how male and female students interact with content and retain learned material (Ogunleye and Adepoju, 2020). Thus, the problem that necessitates this study is the continued use of instructional approaches that may not adequately support students' retention and equitable learning outcomes, particularly in abstract topics like SHM.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to examine the effect of technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction on Physics students' performance and retention in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion, with particular attention to gender differences and comparison with the expository method. The study has the following specific objectives:

1. To investigate the effect of technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction on students' performance in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics.

2. To examine the effect of technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction and expository methods on students' retention in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics.
3. To compare the retention scores of male and female students exposed to the expository method and technology-enhanced guided-inquiry in Simple Harmonic Motion.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the effect of technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction and expository on students' performance in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics?
2. Is there a significant difference in retention scores of students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using technology-enhances guided-inquiry and expository methods?
3. Does gender significantly influence students' retention when taught Simple Harmonic Motion taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry and expository methods.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in retention scores of students in Simple Harmonic motion in Physics taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry and expository methods.

HO₃: There is no significant difference in retention scores between male and female

students in Simple Harmonic Motion taught using technology enhanced guided-inquiry instruction.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design, which involved pretest, posttest, and retention test. Two intact classes were used, one assigned to the Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) group and the other to the Expository group. This design was suitable as it allowed the researcher to observe the natural classroom settings without random assignment, while still measuring the impact of the instructional strategies (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). The study area was Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Itu Local Government is one of the Ibibio tribes in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State with a land mass of approximately 606.1 square kilometers. It is under Itu- Ibiono Ibom Federal Constituency and was created in 1987. The Local Government is bounded in the North and North East by Odukpani in Cross River State and Arochukwu in Abia State respectively. In the West by Ibiono Ibom and Ikono Local Government Areas, in the South and South-East by Uyo and Uruan Local Government Area respectively. The population of the study cut across 998 senior secondary two physics students, the sample size for the study was 108 senior secondary two students purposely drawn from the 10 public secondary schools from the area. A researcher-made instruments titled: Physics Performance Test (PPT) was developed on the concept of Simple Harmonic motion for pretest, posttest and retention. The PPT was made of 50 multiple-choice items, each carried 2 marks; the maximum score for the instrument were 100 marks. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument; the PPT was administered to 20 physics students who were

not part of the main study by using test-retest method, the reliability coefficient of 0.85 was gotten after analyzing the scores with Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). From the analysis, the reliability of the instrument was ascertained.

Experimental Procedure

The experiment lasted six weeks as follows:

- a. Week 1: obtaining permission from the participating schools administrators and the administration of the pretest for both groups.
- b. Weeks 2–3: Teaching of SHM for both experimental and control groups, the experimental groups were taught the concept of SHM using Technology-enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) by the researcher while the control group were taught with the Expository Laboratory by the help of the Physics teacher who served as the research assistant. Immediately after the teaching (treatment), the posttest was administered under the supervision of the research assistants.
- c. The Experimental group were engaged in hands-on investigations through Technology-Enhanced Guide-Inquiry (TEGI) using PhETS imulation and teacher-facilitated the lesson/teaching with probing questions and effective guidance.

- d. The Control received structured lectures and demonstrations, typical of conventional teaching (Expository method).
- e. Week 4-6: Administration of Retention test and scoring. The retention test was a reshuffled version of the instruments PPT administered three weeks after the posttest.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data were collected by administering the PPT on SHM as pretest to students before treatment, after treatment, the posttest was administered and a rearranged version of the instruments were administered three weeks after the posttest as retention test, they were marked and scored and the scores were analyzed accordingly; mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research. Questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the effect of technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction and expository method on students’ performance in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Students Performance in Physics taught using Technology-enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) and those taught using Expository Method.

Group	PRETEST			POSTTEST		
	Mean	Std. Deviation		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental (TEGI)	50	31.12	8.12	73.52	14.99	42.40
Control		29.22	9.66	57.36	10.94	28.14

The analysis of the pretest and posttest scores in Table 1, reveals a clear distinction in

performance improvement between the experimental group taught using technology-

enhanced guided-inquiry and the control group taught through the traditional expository method. Both groups started with similar pretest means (31.12 for experimental and 29.22 for control), indicating comparable prior knowledge. However, after instruction, the experimental group achieved a significantly higher posttest mean of 73.52 compared to 57.36 in the control group. This suggests that the technology-enhanced guided-inquiry method was more effective in enhancing students' understanding of Simple Harmonic Motion. The greater mean difference in the experimental group (42.40) compared to the control group (28.14) further supports this conclusion. Although the standard deviation increased in both groups, the wider spread in the experimental group (14.99) indicates varied individual performance gains,

likely due to differences in students' interaction with the technology tools. Overall, the result demonstrates that integrating technology with guided-inquiry provides a more impactful learning experience, leading to better academic performance in Physics.

Research Question2

Is there a significant difference in retention scores of students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using technology-enhances guided-inquiry and expository methods?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Posttest and Retention Scores of Students Performance in Physics taught using Technology- Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) and those taught using Expository Method.

Group	N	POSTTEST		RETENTION		Mean Difference
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Experimental (TEGI)	50	73.52	14.99	61.36	11.01	12.16
Control	58	57.36	10.94	47.29	11.01	10.07

The result of the analysis in Table 2 reveals a clear and meaningful distinction between the experimental and control groups in terms of both posttest performance and retention scores. Students in the experimental group, who were taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry, achieved a mean posttest score of 73.52 with a standard deviation of 14.99, while the control group, taught through the expository method, recorded a mean score of 57.36 with a standard deviation of 10.94. This indicates that not only did the experimental group outperform the control group, but there was also a wider spread of scores, suggesting varying levels of benefit among students in the guided-inquiry group. In terms of retention, the experimental group again demonstrated higher achievement,

with a mean retention score of 61.36 compared to 47.29 in the control group. Interestingly, both groups had the same standard deviation (11.01), implying consistent variability in retention within each group. The higher mean score for the experimental group reflects the lasting impact of guided-inquiry methods supported by technology, which actively engaged students in constructing knowledge and reinforced understanding over time. These findings suggest that technology-enhanced guided-inquiry is more effective not only for immediate performance but also for long-term knowledge retention.

Research Question 3

Does gender significantly influence students’ retention when taught Simple Harmonic Motion taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry instruction?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Male and Female Students’ taught Physics with Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) and Expository Methods

Strategy	Gender	N	POSTTEST		RETENTIONTEST		Mean Difference
			Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	
Experimental (TEGI)	Male	22	73.68	13.88	60.68	11.33	13.00
	Female	28	73.39	16.05	61.89	10.93	11.50

The comparison of posttest and retention scores in Table 3 between male and female students in the experimental group, who were taught Simple Harmonic Motion using Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI), reveals an insightful trend. While both genders demonstrated nearly identical posttest scores (73.68 for males and 73.39 for females), the retention scores showed a slight advantage for females (61.89) over males (60.68). This indicates that although immediate performance levels were equivalent, female students retained the learned concepts marginally better over time. The standard deviation for both posttest (13.88 males; 16.05 females) and retention (11.33 males; 10.93 females) suggests a consistent

spread in scores, with females exhibiting slightly greater variation in the posttest phase but more consistency in retention.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the performance scores of students in Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics taught using technology-enhanced guided-inquiry and expository methods.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of Students’ Performance taught Physics with Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry(TEGI) and those taught with Expository method (n=108).

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Pretest	69.499	1	69.499	.411	.523
Strategy	7079.637	1	7079.637	41.855	.000*
Residual	17760.377	105	169.146		
Total	478933.000	108			

As presented in Table 4, the calculated p-value (.000) is less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference between the groups. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the method of instruction had a significant impact on students’

performance in Simple Harmonic Motion. Specifically, students taught using the Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) approach outperformed those taught with the traditional Expository method. The result highlights the

effectiveness of the TEGI strategy in improving Physics students' academic performance.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in retention scores of students in Simple Harmonic motion in

Physics taught using Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry and Expository Methods.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of Students' Retention taught Physics with Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry and those taught with Expository

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Posttest	400.274	1	400.274	3.374	.069
Strategy	2614.045	1	2614.045	22.037	.000*
Residual	12455.264	105	118.622		
Total	330833.000	108			

As shown in Table 5, the calculated p-value (.000) is less than the alpha level of 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a statistically significant difference in the mean retention scores of Physics students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using Technology- Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) and those taught with the Expository method. The result suggests that the observed difference in retention is unlikely to be due to random chance, implying that the instructional strategy had a substantial effect on students' ability to retain Physics concepts. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected in favor

of the alternative, affirming the positive impact of TEGI on students' retention.

Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in retention scores between male and female students in Simple Harmonic Motion taught using technology enhanced guided-inquiry instruction.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance of Retention Scores Between Male and Female Students taught Physics with Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) Method (50).

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Posttest	2.101	1	2.101	.017	.898
Gender	17.948	1	17.948	.142	.708
Residual	5923.350	47	126.029		
Total	194196.000	50			

As shown in Table 6, the calculated p-value (.708) exceeds the alpha level of 0.05, leading to the retention of the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics using the Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) method. The result suggests that

gender did not play a significant role in students' retention of Physics concepts when exposed to the TEGI instructional approach, highlighting its effectiveness in promoting equitable learning outcomes across genders.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry and Expository method on Academic Performance in Physics: The findings of the present study showing a significant difference in Physics performance between students taught with technology-enhanced guided-inquiry and those taught with the expository method are strongly supported by recent Nigerian research. For instance, Achor et al. (2021) and Umar and Musa (2020) found that guided-inquiry, especially when integrated with tools like PhET simulations, improves understanding and achievement in Physics by fostering active engagement and visual interaction with abstract concepts. Similarly, Okoye and Onah (2022) reported that technology-assisted instruction leads to better academic outcomes than traditional lecture-based methods. However, Adediran & Ibrahim (2021) offered a counterpoint, noting no significant difference in some contexts, suggesting that factors like teacher competence, topic difficulty, and student readiness may influence outcomes. Overall, the weight of evidence affirms that guided-inquiry, particularly when supported by technology, enhances students' academic performance in Physics.

Effect of Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry and Expository method on Knowledge Retention in Physics: The study found that students taught Simple Harmonic Motion using Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) retained Physics concepts significantly better than those taught through the traditional Expository method which showed significant difference in retention between those taught with TEGI and Expository methods. This outcome aligns with several recent Nigerian studies, including Achor et al. (2021), Okoli and Eze (2021), and Usman and Bello (2020), which reported that guided-inquiry approaches, especially when supported with simulations, lead to deeper understanding and long-term retention. Additionally, Nwafor and Ugwuanyi (2020) examined the influence of inquiry-based learning on

secondary school students' academic retention in Enugu State. Their results indicated that guided-inquiry not only improved comprehension but also supported long-term memory due to learners' active construction of knowledge. Collectively, these empirical studies affirm that TEGI provides a more impactful and equitable instructional approach than expository methods, particularly in promoting sustained understanding of abstract scientific content. These methods actively engage learners, allowing them to explore and visualize concepts more effectively than passive lecture-based instruction. Thus, TEGI proves to be a more effective strategy for improving retention in Physics education.

Effect of Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) on Students' Retention in Physics and Gender: The result of the analysis revealed that there was no significant difference in retention scores between male and female students taught Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics using Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI). Although minor variations existed in the mean retention scores (male = 60.68, female = 61.89), the difference was not statistically significant, indicating that both genders benefited equally from the instructional approach. This suggests that TEGI is a gender-inclusive strategy that supports cognitive development and knowledge retention irrespective of sex. This finding aligns with those of Eze and Eya (2020), who observed that guided-inquiry with computer simulations improved retention across gender lines in Physics classrooms. Similarly, Obi and Aladejana (2021) reported no significant gender difference in retention when secondary students were exposed to digital inquiry-based instruction, attributing this to the engaging and supportive nature of the strategy. In the same vein, Adeyemi and Ibe (2022) concluded that gender had no meaningful influence on retention when interactive technologies were employed alongside inquiry-based learning in science classes.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that the use of Technology-Enhanced Guided-Inquiry (TEGI) significantly improves students' academic performance and retention in the concept of Simple Harmonic Motion in Physics compared to the traditional expository method. The strategy promotes active engagement, deeper conceptual understanding, and long-term memory of learned content. Additionally, the study revealed no significant difference in retention scores between male and female students taught using TEGI, indicating that the method supports equitable learning outcomes across genders. These results highlight the effectiveness of integrating technology and inquiry-based approaches in Physics education to foster meaningful and inclusive learning experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made to improve students' performance and retention in Physics:

1. Physics teachers should utilize and encourage students on the use of student-centered strategies to deliver lesson as it promotes flexible, autonomous and independent learning.
2. Physics teachers should adopt Technology-Enhances Strategies like guided-inquiry in classroom.
3. Government and education stakeholders should train teacher on more Technology- enhance methods.
4. Physics teachers should motivate boys and girls to learn effectively to avoid gender disparities in performance and knowledge retention.

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